

LABOR RELATIONS UNDER PRIVATE INTERNATIONAL LAW

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Abstract

This article talks about the doctrine of private international law, its development, and labor relations in it.

Key words

international law, person, subject, social, political, economic, citizen, marriage, law.

As a subject of international law, the Republic of Uzbekistan has its place on the world political map and has been cooperating with other countries, international organizations, associations, and companies on issues related to various spheres of social life. . This, in turn, requires knowledge of and compliance with international laws aimed at regulating this relationship. Socio-economic relations between citizens of different states, foreign citizens and stateless persons residing in any state, as well as legal entities and states are regulated by international private law norms.

International private law is a separate field of law recognized as a branch of legal science in the system of private law. This field is a private one that takes place in the context of international life. that is, it includes family, labor, business, and economic procedural relations regulated by civil law and civil procedural law. The regulation of the creation, change and annulment of this relationship between citizens and legal entities of different countries, as well as the resolution of the relationship in the event of a dispute, have their own characteristics. 0 The Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan (Article 1158 of the Civil Code) defines relations regulated by international private law norms as civil-legal relations complicated by a foreign elementA complicated relationship with a foreign element is widespread, the subjects of foreign law belong to the citizenship of different countries, their objects are located in the territory of different countries, for the creation, change and cancellation of this relationship. It requires evaluation of the underlying legal facts through the law of a specific country, prevention, elimination, and resolution of the conflict in a specific area and at the right time. In international life, the types of problems like this can be different, so it is impossible

to limit it to any list. Therefore, they cause the relationship to be complicated in different circumstances. Some international documents and agreements take a special place in the complexity of private-legal relations. These include the 1928 Bustamante Code (Private International Law Code), the 1980 UN Convention on International Sales Contracts, the 1988 Convention on International Financial Leasing, Warsaw Convention of 1929 for the Unification of Certain Regulations Relating to International Air Routes, Geneva Convention of 1956 on Contracts for the Carriage of Cargo by International Airway, 1967 Stockholm Convention "On the Establishment of the World Intellectual Property Organization", 1994 UN Convention "On the Immunity of States and Their Property", 2002 "Civil, Family, Criminal Cases" Chisinau Convention on Mutual Legal Assistance and others. By means of these sources, a number of private-legal relations, concepts, and procedures for their regulation, complicated by the foreign element, are defined.

Private international law refers to international decisions that aim to ensure to all people the rights and freedoms that have historically been considered "fundamental". These rights are established for all people and are not limited by nationality or territory.

1. Equal rights and freedoms of all people.
2. Provision of rights and freedoms that can be used independently by states and international organizations based on the international legal system.
3. Compliance with international laws and documents and organizations that have adopted rights.
4. The need to get acquainted with all the foundations of international private law, comply with them and use them.
5. On the basis of the laws, documents and agreements adopted by the states to ensure human rights, the rights of people to fair view, to hold on to immutability, and to face problems with attention are summarized.
6. Emphasizing the symbolic visions of independence, territoriality and international relations of each state in the form of state policy combined with private international law.
7. In the form of a state policy that requires the reflection of each individual, taking into account the considered information about the situation of injustice, each state ensures justice, order and law in its territory and in relations with international organizations. 'to provide.
8. Openly announce international laws, human rights documents, treaties and state policies to other countries and international organizations.

9. Provide information and receive information to ensure that all people are familiar with, offer and use private international law.

Labor relations under private international law include the application of rules and principles to resolve disputes arising in international labor relations. These conflicts include issues such as jurisdiction, choice of law, recognition and enforcement of labor contracts and labor rights in different countries. Principles of private international law help determine which national laws should govern labor relations, which courts have jurisdiction over labor disputes, and how judgments and awards are recognized and enforced internationally.

For example, if an employee works in a foreign country, private international law determines whether the employment contract is governed by the laws of the country where the work is performed or the laws of the employee's home country. It also helps determine which court has jurisdiction over potential disputes. Private international law plays a crucial role in ensuring fairness and consistency in cross-border labor relations. However, this can be complex and legal advice is advised when dealing with employment matters involving multiple jurisdictions.

International private law, labor relations, defined in international documents on this subject, including documents adopted by the International Labor Organization (ILO). The ILO is an international organization of great importance in drafting and implementing laws related to the provision of uniform labor rights, access to work and other labor relations issues. On the basis of private rights, basic principles are presented that allow each person to perform labor activities freely and without injustice. These principles include:

1. Free choice: Everyone should have free choices about their work and profession.

2. Temporality: Employment contracts should be drawn up based on the principle of temporality.

3. Protection from unfair work: Should be protected from situations involving dangerous and unpleasant working conditions.

4. Social protection: Every worker must be protected by social protection and guarantees in the form of entrepreneurship.

In the field of labor relations, international organizations, governments, manufacturing enterprises and public organizations are of great importance. Their task is to ensure the single right of labor, eliminate work-related problems, and ensure that the workplace is in a safe and orderly place. Labor relations under private international law foster the spirit of cooperation and allow people to fight against injustice and freedom. This requires comprehensive cooperation in order to

provide people with healthy living conditions based on the independence of relations and protection from unfair work.

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